

Short Communication

OF SUITABLE

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Abstract

Two ugly persons are well matched. They have no attractive power. It is their demerit. As such they have no followers. None gives them liking. So there is no unhealthy competition. As such it is their merit. They enjoy both merit and demerit simultaneously. It is quite rare. They are the only best suitable partner.

Key words: Suitable, right, appropriate, acceptable, adapted, satisfying, able, qualified

Introduction

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Suitable is right or appropriate for a particular person, purpose, or situation. For example: These toys are not suitable for children under five.

It is acceptable or right for someone or something. For example: The film is not suitable for children.

It is adapted to a use or purpose e.g., suitable for kitchen use.

It is satisfying propriety. It means proper e.g., suitable dress.

It is able. It is qualified e.g., a suitable candidate for the job.

Suitable is not static. It is a dynamic concept. It always changes. Also it causes change. Someone may consider something suitable in the morning. He may reject the same as unsuitable in the evening of that very day. Even what is accepted as suitable right now, may appear as unsuitable in the very next moment. This variation is liable for the variation either in changed situation or whims or both simultaneously.

Someone considers someone suitable. Also he may consider that person unsuitable. He is either fickle-minded or moody or both simultaneously. Thus his mood and motive are gloriously so uncertain. Such a person is difficult to handle. None can choose anything on his behalf. Also none wants to choose to avoid complication. Sometimes he accepts third party's

decision. Sometimes he accepts not. So what he thinks suitable is difficult to guess thereby gauge. Even he knows not what he will choose.

In a conservative society the parents choose their bride and groom for their sons and daughters. The guardians judge the suitable candidate. Their decision is considered as final more, than suitable. It is top to bottom not bottom to top policy of management science. In reality it may or may not be suitable. It is imposed not composed. So many times it gets decomposed. The patriarchal society seldom cares for voice. They want to do good but its outcome is bad. For the fact is that if the whip is declined most of the time the unfortunate souls face honour killing.

The sons and daughters may have choice but the voice of parents is final. The members of such an orthodox society simply marry their allotted candidate without any objection. Also the parents are bound to carry out the order of the society. They cannot plead on behalf of their issues regarding their personal choice. They are quite helpless in this regard. Both parents and their issues cannot escape from the strict vigilance and stern thousand eyes around them round the clock.

The paradox is that the couples of this conservative society lead a happy conjugal life. It seems they get the gift of classical decision of their parents. In contrast, the persons who marry through self-choice suffer from divorce. Thus, if the former is classical success the latter is an artistic failure. The former is blessed and the latter is cursed.

Suitable is the outcome of both qualitative and quantitative judgement. In case of emotion the decision regarding suitability is guided by qualitative norms. It varies person to person. It manifests the characteristic nature and behaviour of any concerned person. Also it discloses the cultural heritage of any person in question.

In scientific investigation suitable involves quantitative decision. It means exact. It deals with correctness. Also in business and accountancy quantitative is the tool for exchange. Here emotion has no room. Profit is the single agenda of all the parties involved.

The best choice is one which satisfies both qualitative and quantitative test. It may be called acid test. It is ideal in nature. Ideal is always unattainable. As such they call it unattainable ideal. Hence it is rare.

In democracy people may raise their voice independently. They enjoy liberal environment. In dictatorship there is no room for such free voice or choice. People may have choice but voice of the tyrant is final.

Suitable is a matter of luck. Also it involves ill-luck. Thus it may be both fortune and misfortune. Man experiences it in family and office life.

Marriage is a long journey. Tolerance is its only fuel. Before marriage a person can consider suitability. He can enjoy that democratic right. After marriage and giving birth to children the matter suitability should be avoided for the sake of wife and more for the welfare of children. Someone does not care for any bondage. He declines all relations. He leaves the present partner and begins to leave with another better suitable partner. He farewells welfare.

There is good. There is better. There is best. Also there is better than best. After few days the person leaves in search of another better than best beauty. It is an endless episode of an infinite series. Such a person suffers from insanity. So he finds none suitable. Also he is not suitable to anybody. Everybody knows it except himself.

Two lovers may consider them suitable. They consider them as either made for each other or mad for each other or both for both simultaneously. They perceive that they will not exist in absence of the other. Then they may marry. Or they may not marry. But they start to live together. Enjoyment suits them but bondage not.

They are so sly. They may or may not give birth to children. Both are their democratic right. Then one fine morning they discover that they are not suitable further to each other. Either one of them or both find someone more suitable. They leave each other for better option.

This decision has two outcomes. The first outcome is that they get relief from boring life. They enjoy more with better suitable new partner.

The second simultaneous outcome is that the children are deserted. They get shelter in the orphan house. Thus the orphan houses become over-crowded getting regular and uninterrupted supply of human babes. This is the outcome of suitable modern jet life.

Such neglected children become prodigal being deprived from mother's affection. They become criminal. It seems unguarded childhood coupled with unshaded infant offered them such unique identity. They are not considered as the member of the main stream of the society. None loves them. Everybody hates them. None laughs for them. Everybody laughs at them. Everybody can avoid them. But their existence cannot be declined. Thus live together is not illegal. It is immoral.

One cannot choose his boss. One cannot choose his subordinates. The authority makes the group and imposes the decision. The employee is not offered or delegated the power of such choice of group formation. Then they will be engaged more in change than work. It will invite poor work culture with strong politics as bonus.

The doctor knows what is suitable for the patient. Similarly, the parents know what is suitable for their children. Rich garments render the children glad. But a poor person cannot afford it. He purchases as per his capacity. As such they say, "Cut your coat according to your cloth".

In future if the person earns much he enjoys and gives rich food or garments or any other costly things to all his deprived family members. Also they become happy for fulfilling their long-cherished desire. But an alert person never meets up the demand of the children immediate. It renders them prodigal. They do not learn the value of hard earned money. The

immature child does not learn to wait. Waiting is a great virtue. One has to learn it to conquer future hurdles thereby builds the career.

Two rich persons match well. People think that they are either of equal merit or equal status or both simultaneously. This assumption may or may not be correct. Also these two persons do not think so. So they speak cautiously or keep safe distance lest they come closer which they want not at first sight. They are suitable to each other only when they are frank and exchange sweet words accordingly. Here equal respect enhances the suitability.

Similarly two poor persons feel for each other. They have nothing. Nothingness is their ever companion from cradle to coffin. They feel comfort to stay together. If they do not quarrel then they become suitable neighbours. All the presidents of all nations are equal in status. But they differ in financial strength. They are alike by designation but differ in limitation. The rich president does suffer from superiority complex. The poor president does suffer from inferiority complex. So rich nation is not suitable for poor nation. However, complex of any kind is not good at all. Ultimately, it suits none.

Two heroines seldom are suitable for each other regarding cooperation. Both are careerist. Careerist is always selfish. Both hanker after glamour. Complexion does not last long. Similarly demand is unstable thereby causes tension. Thus two heroines are not suitable friends. They seldom embrace each other.

Similarly, two heroes are rivals to each other. Due to rivalry a hero even murder another hero to make the career free from all hurdles. In this regard the unholy relation with the underground world is very dangerous. Here financial transaction is the main controlling factor.

In magnetism of physics like pole repels and unlike pole attracts. So both hero and heroine having beautiful complexion repel each other due to unhealthy competition. They suffer from personality conflict.

A beautiful heroine likes to stay with an ugly woman to highlight her beauty more. Here instant comparison of the eyes around ignites her pride that titillates her ego. Thus unlike beauty attracts. This is equally true in case of heroes also.

Two ugly persons are well matched. They have no attractive power. It is their demerit. As such they have no followers. None gives them liking. So there is no unhealthy competition. As such it is their merit. They enjoy both merit and demerit simultaneously. It is quite rare. They are the only best suitable partner.

School dress stands for uniformity, equality and fraternity. It levels all pupils hailing from all walks of life. It binds all tender souls together and strengthens bondage among them. It teaches ethics. It teaches all are equal and at par. This moral principle paves the way for future success. Here lies the suitability of school dress. Here lies its essence. The eloquent voices of childhood are quite nostalgic. Later on it renders someone indifferent in careless moment.

In hot weather country winter season is suitable for tour and picnic. In cold weather country hot weather is suitable for enjoyment.

In family life both hot and cold treatment are equally suitable for balancing the relations. Extreme of either strategy i.e., too hot or too cold is not suitable at all. In case of too hot treatment the children ultimately become unruly. They become seasoned of beating and corporal punishment i.e., any kind of physical torture. Such children disobey their parents.

Similarly, in case of too much cold policy the children go as per their sweet

will. They become guideless. They become diverted. They are trapped by evil company. Here the parents did not discharge their duties properly. They are simply parents without any responsibility. They are like a ship without radar. They can never reach their destination. In this regard intelligent persons enjoy unlimited but seldom gives birth to children to avoid ill-fame and future hazards.

As such, neither too hot nor too cold rather in between or medium or optimum is the best of all. Thus neither leftist nor rightist is suitable. Middle East is the best or most suitable.

In case of interrogation of criminals there are various types of procedures thus followed. If the criminal tells all and confesses all and everything early then the criminal is not punished if the statements are found true after proper verification. Otherwise third degree operation is applied in the police station. Most of the persons cannot bear torture. Almost all persons confess the truth in fear of corporal punishment. Thus the suitability of application of third degree cannot be overstated.

The police personnel finds the truth applying various types of innovative mechanism on various criminals in different forms and features having different degrees and dimensions as well. Every criminal is unique. Application is also unique accordingly. Really it is a difficult task. Only a wearer knows where the shoe pinches. Obviously, one school of thought declines and protests against any kind of torture be they physical or mental or cocktail of both in different proportions. They contend that it is against fundamental human right.

There are various forms of governments. If the citizens are unruly then dictatorship is suitable to size the public as is believed by a shrewd politician. If public are gentle in nature then democracy is suitable. Half democracy or half dictatorship is absurd and not good at all. In that case full dictatorship is better than half democracy. Half works less but obstructs more. It demands profit, declines loss. Full works well always. Full means full power. Half is ready to take profit but not loss. It hankers after asset avoids liability. It knows not that half is a liability, not asset to the society. Profit is his single agenda. He is suitable nowhere.

Mother knows what is suitable to her children. She does it since the little kids do lack in reasoning power. Later on the child grows older. He acquires the power of choice. If at that older age he depends on third party's opinion it proves his deficiency. It causes irritation. This personality trait is not suitable at all for an adult individual.

CONCLUSION

Someone is suitable to someone. He or she may not be suitable to another one. But there is someone who is popular to all. He or she is liked by all. Such a person is culture free. He or she possesses universal face. Hero or heroine is selected from this angle of face value. Similarly, baby and bud are liked by all. Both sun rise and sun set enchant a romantic heart. Every sun set guarantees another sun rise in the very next morning. Thus both suit the optimist and pessimist souls through synergy.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.

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